

DRUG RESISTANT EPILEPTIC ENCEPHALOPATHY WITH LATE-ONSET SPASMS

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Introduction. Developmental and epileptic encephalopathy (DEE) is a term used to describe cerebral dysfunction resulting from the underlying cause, epilepsy, or both. There is a subset of DEEs in which there is compelling evidence that the regression is directly tied to the epilepsy itself, where the “epileptic encephalopathy” component of DEE is most evident. Infantile epileptic spasm syndrome (IESS) is perhaps the clearest example.

Throughout the past, several decades scattered publications have noted, however, that there are patients that present with apparent epileptic encephalopathies associated with spasms and other seizures in between the common ages of presentation for IESS and LGS. For this, a separate condition has been proposed with various names including “Late-onset Infantile Spasms,” “Infantile Epileptic Encephalopathy with Late-onset Spasms,” and “Late Infantile Epileptic Encephalopathy.” There are differences in the nuances of the descriptions, but common features are onset of spasms, spasm-tonic, and myoclonic-tonic seizures beyond the first year of life with a lack of obvious prenatal or perinatal causes in many cases.

Some DEE syndromes could be considered likely epileptic encephalopathies including early infantile developmental epileptic encephalopathy (EIDEE), infantile epileptic spasm syndrome (IESS), and Lennox-Gastaut syndrome (LGS). However, within the spectrum of DEE exists a distinct syndrome which has been variously described as “late-onset infantile spasms,” “cryptogenic late-onset epileptic spasms,” “infantile epileptic encephalopathy with late-onset spasms,” and “late infantile epileptic encephalopathy (LIEE).

Purpose: This study aimed to analyze patients with proto-typical features of these patients in order to evaluate the prevalence, demography, and specific clinical and electrographic characteristics. In this paper, we use the term late infantile epileptic encephalopathy (LIEE) to describe these patients, although the precise title is not of paramount importance.

After the first year of life, epileptic spasms known as late-onset spasms (LOS) occur. Our objective was to evaluate the electroclinical characteristics and follow-up of patients experiencing this specific kind of epileptic seizure.

Methods: Between 2020 and 2024, we retrospectively included all patients whose LOS was verified by electroencephalography. At diagnosis and during follow-up, clinical and electroencephalographic results were gathered. The neuropsychological result was assessed using the Vineland scale.

Results: Out of 211 patients with documented epileptic spasms, we describe 11 patients with LOS. With late-onset spasms, eleven patients suffered from epileptic encephalopathy. A localized or widespread discharge of triphasic slow waves, slow spikes, or slow spikes waves with fast activity was observed on the ictal electroencephalography (EEG). In the absence of hypsarhythmia, the interictal EEG typically displayed low spike waves or focused or widespread slow waves. Of the patients, only two had managed LOS. Six experienced a severe epileptic encephalopathy, and three acquired the classic Lennox-Gastaut syndrome. Eleven patients had their neuropsychological outcomes assessed using the Vineland scale. Of the 11 patients, 10 had mild to severe cognitive delay, and only one had normal cognitive skills.

Conclusion: After the age of one, epileptic spasms may manifest. Patients who suffer from epileptic encephalopathy are more likely to experience these. A small number of people experienced this kind of seizure prior to meeting the criteria for Lennox-Gastaut syndrome. We identified focal epilepsy in one patient, who had cluster seizures. Refractory epilepsy and severe cognitive outcomes unrelated to the etiology appear to be associated with epileptic syndromes when LOS are associated with an epileptic encephalopathy.

This study has some limitations, such as the relatively small sample size and short data collection period. Additionally, developmental status and seizures outside of those observed during EEGs were based on parent and guardian descriptions. While the developmental status reported in this study reflects the baseline at the onset of LIEE, it would be advantageous to also characterize the developmental status at the onset of epilepsy, considering the nature of developmental and epileptic encephalopathies. Future studies on LIEE would benefit from a larger sample size and a multicenter prospective design to assess its etiology, presenting seizure type(s), electroclinical features, and treatment options

References:

1. Zuberi SM, Wirrell E, Yozawitz E, Wilmschurst JM, Specchio N, Riney K, et al. ILAE classification and definition of epilepsy syndromes with onset in neonates

and infants: position statement by the ILAE task force on nosology and definitions. *Epilepsia*. 2022;63(6):1349–97. <https://doi.org/10.1111/epi.17239>

2. Scheffer IE, Liao J. Deciphering the concepts behind "epileptic encephalopathy" and "developmental and epileptic encephalopathy". *Eur J Paediatr Neurol*. 2020; 24:11–4. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpn.2019.12.0233>

3. Ohtahara S. Epileptic encephalopathies of infancy. *Neurology Asia*; 2007

4. Nordli DR Jr. Epileptic encephalopathies in infants and children. *J Clin Neurophysiol*. 2012;29(5):420–4. <https://doi.org/10.1097/WNP.0b013e31826bd961>

5. Eisermann MM, Ville D, Soufflet C, Plouin P, Chiron C, Dulac O, et al. Cryptogenic late-onset epileptic spasms: an overlooked syndrome of early childhood? *Epilepsia*. 2006;47:1035–42

6. Auvin S, Lamblin MD, Pandit F, Vallée L, Bouvet-Mourcia A. Infantile epileptic encephalopathy with late-onset spasms: report of 19 patients. *Epilepsia*. 2010 Jul; 51(7):1290–6. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1528-1167.2010.02534.x7>

7. Nordli DR Jr, Korff CM, Goldstein J, Koh S, Laux L, Kelley KR. Cryptogenic late-onset epileptic spasms or late infantile epileptogenic encephalopathy? *Epilepsia*. 2007;48(1):206–8. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1528-1167.2007.00978_2.x8

8. Matsumoto A, Watanabe K, Negoro T, Sugiura M, Iwase K, Hara K, et al. Infantile spasms: etiological factors, clinical aspects, and long term prognosis in 200 cases. *Eur J Pediatr*. 1981;135:239–44

9. Majnemer A, Shevell MI. Diagnostic yield of the neurologic assessment of the developmentally delayed child. *J Pediatr*. 1995;127:193–9. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3476\(95\)70294-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3476(95)70294-6)

10. Kwan P, Arzimanoglou A, Berg AT, Brodie MJ, Allen Hauser W, Mathern G, et al. Definition of drug resistant epilepsy: consensus proposal by the ad hoc task force of the ILAE commission on therapeutic strategies. *Epilepsia*. 2010; 51(6):1069–77. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1528-1167.2009.02397.x> Epub 2009 Nov 3. Erratum in: *Epilepsia*. 2010 Sep;51(9):1922

11. Gibbs EL, Fleming MM, Gibbs FA. Diagnosis and prognosis of hypsarrhythmia and infantile spasms. *Pediatrics*. 1954;13:66–73.

12. Fusco L, Vigevano F. Ictal clinical electroencephalographic findings of spasms in west syndrome. *Epilepsia*. 1993;34(4):671–8